

Studies on the Bi-ionic Potential and the Mobility Ratios with Resin-membrane Electrodes and Their Behaviour in a Mixture of Critical Ions

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The 'mobility ratios' in resin membranes for a number of ion pairs, viz., $\text{Na}^+ - \text{K}^+$, $\text{I}^- - \text{Br}^-$, $\text{Br}^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Cl}^-$, and $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Br}^-$, have been calculated from measurement of bi-ionic potential observing at the same time the influence of ionic strength on them. The 'mobility ratio' values of different resin-membrane electrodes are not as widely different for a pair of ions as would be desirable for a satisfactory evaluation of the unknown activities in a binary mixture of critical ions using Marshall's equation. The behaviour of resin-membrane electrodes towards a mixture of critical ions has been studied with $\text{K}^+ - \text{Na}^+$, $\text{Br}^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{Br}^- - \text{NO}_3^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Cl}^-$, and $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Br}^-$ mixtures with activity ratios varying from 100 to 1 to find the influence of the second ion on the membrane which has been initially saturated with the first ion on both sides. The second ion begins to affect the E.M.F. as soon as its activity is above a certain value which has been found to be different for different ion pairs.

The membrane electrodes, whether of collodion, clay, or synthetic resins, are limited in their application to the determination of the activity even of a single species, viz., of the critical ion. The limitation is all the more pronounced when more than one critical or potential-determining ions are present, each species of which makes a contribution to the measured potential, depending on its activity in solution and its mobility within the membrane. So the necessity of finding out a factor which will measure the relative contribution of each ionic species to the transport of electricity across the membrane has been realised by various workers¹⁻⁴. The attempt was made by Sollner³ in defining a term 'intramembrane transference number' in connection with collodion membrane and by Marshall⁵⁻⁶ and Wyllie⁷ in finding out a term 'intramembrane mobility ratio' in clay and resin membranes respectively. The transference number or the mobility ratio factor can be calculated from the measured values of B. I. P. (*vide infra*).

When an ion-exchange membrane is interposed between two solutions of the same electrolyte having the same critical cation or the anion but of different concentrations and hence of different activity, the potential difference developed is called the concentration potential or the dialysis potential. The sign and magnitude of this E.M.F. are a measure of the selectivity of the membrane towards the ions of an electrolyte. But when the membrane separates solutions, each of which contains a different critical ion, the state of affairs

1. Wyllie and Patnode, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 204.
2. McLean *et al.*, *Soil Sci.*, 1951, **72**, 315.
3. *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1948, **53**, 1211, 1226; 1950, **54**, 743.
4. Dray and Sollner, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1955, **18**, 341; 1956, **21**, 126; 1956, **22**, 213.
5. Marshall, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 1284.
6. Marshall and Mukherjee, *ibid.*, 1951, **55**, 61.
7. Wyllie, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 67.

becomes somewhat different. The simplest picture is when the membrane separates solutions having the same concentration of two different critical ions, to each of which the membrane is permeable, and also the same 'non-critical' ion to which the membrane is completely impermeable. The potential difference measured between the two sides of a membrane in this particular case has been termed bi-ionic potential or B.I.P. which is a measure of the selectivity of a membrane for ions of the same sign.

Sollner³ made a thorough study of bi-ionic potentials. He suggested the most probable mechanism of the origin of B. I. P. and discussed different factors influencing its magnitude and sign. He extended his studies to 'polyionic potentials'⁴ across membranes of ideal ionic selectivity in systems with more than two species of critical ions and used the formula of B.I.P. as:

$$\text{Uni-univalent } E = \pm \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{t_1}{t_2} \quad \begin{array}{l} (+\text{for cation selective}) \\ (-\text{for anion selective}) \end{array}$$

where t_1 and t_2 are the transference number of the ions (1) and (2) within the membrane.

Marshall^{5,6} discussed the origin of the B.I.P., like potential across clay membranes, which are considered to be non-porous in character. The method is based on the assumptions that a membrane gives rise to a potential by reducing the mobility of the non-critical ion to zero. This potential may be treated as the limiting case of a liquid-junction potential. The Henderson equation⁸ is utilised directly, setting anion mobilities equal to zero in the case of the negatively charged clay membranes. Thus the formula for, say, a uni-univalent ion of the cell:

is, according to Marshall, given by

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{K}^+}}{a_{\text{Na}^+}} \frac{U_{\text{K}^+}}{U_{\text{Na}^+}}$$

Wyllie^{7,9} has derived an equation for multi-ionic potential which can be reduced for a system of two ions to a form similar to that derived by Marshall.

In case of a mixture of critical ions, two methods appear possible for the evaluation from the observed potentials of the activities of several co-existing species of ions. First, membranes, which show a high degree of selectivity for any particular critical ion, may be used for the determination of the activity of that ion alone. Other ions present would be virtually excluded from the membrane phase and these contribute but little to the membrane potential. Clay membranes of this nature were tried by McLean *et al.*² for determination of K^+ -ion activity in presence of Ca^{2+} ion. Permselective collodion membranes also show, according to Sollner³, a rather high degree of selectivity for univalent over bivalent ions and seem to be adaptable to the determination of activity of univalent cations as well as anions in presence of bi- and polyvalent ions of the same sign.

Another approach, worked out by McLean *et al.*², and applied with considerable success to cations using clay membranes, is based on the fact that membranes prepared from

8. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, **59**, 118; 1908, **63**, 325.

9. Wyllie and Kannan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 73.

different clays and under different conditions may have different mobility ratios for the same cationic pair. By combining the data of a particular mixture of ions with two such different membranes, it is possible to evaluate the individual activities in the mixture. The equations used by Marshall and his co-workers⁵⁻⁶ in uni-univalent case are :

$$E = -\frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{I}}}{a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}} + \frac{U_{\text{K}^+}}{U_{\text{Na}^+}} \cdot a_{\text{K}^+}^{\text{II}}}$$

When two membrane materials are available for which $U_{\text{K}^+}/U_{\text{Na}^+}$ has different values, we have two different E.M.F. values for the same mixture with two different membranes, viz.,

$$E_1 = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{I}}}{a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}} + \left(\frac{U_{\text{K}^+}}{U_{\text{Na}^+}}\right)_1 \cdot a_{\text{K}^+}^{\text{II}}}$$

and

$$E_2 = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{I}}}{a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}} + \left(\frac{U_{\text{K}^+}}{U_{\text{Na}^+}}\right)_2 \cdot a_{\text{K}^+}^{\text{II}}}$$

By solving these two simultaneous equations, $a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}}$ and $a_{\text{K}^+}^{\text{II}}$ may be evaluated. An important requirement is the constancy of the $U_{\text{K}^+}/U_{\text{Na}^+}$ values in the range of ionic strength in which the experiments are carried out. For clay membranes, this is often a difficult condition² to achieve.

The present communication deals with a series of measurements of B.I.P. with the object of evaluating the mobility ratios for different ion pairs, particularly of anions. The constancy or the variation of the mobility ratios with concentration has been studied and attempts have been made, based on Marshall's ideas, to ascertain to what extent the resin membranes are applicable for the determination of activity of ions in a mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

Membranes used for the measurements were prepared by the usual procedure by mixing powdered (<200 mesh) commercial cation-exchange resins, viz., IRA-100, Ionac-C-200, Amberlite IR-120, and anion-exchange resins, viz., Ionac-A-300, Amberlite IR-4B, and IR-400, with powdered polystyrene acting as the binder, in a definite proportion and moulding the mixture at 4000 p.s.i. in a hydraulic press at 125-40°C. The membranes prepared were cut into small sizes and were attached to the flanged ends of pyrex tubings with 'Durofix' adhesive. The membranes recording zero asymmetry potential were selected for further studies. For this purpose as well as for obtaining a steady state, the membrane surfaces were kept for 2 to 3 days in contact with the same concentration of the ions, the activity of which was intended to measure. Occasionally the solutions were changed

with the fresh ones. The range of solutions chosen is in accordance with the range in which the membrane electrodes obey the Nernst equation. In the case of a mixture of critical ions, on one side the solution was repeatedly changed until a steady value was obtained.

The E.M.F. readings were made with the help of two tiny saturated calomel electrodes, placed on the two sides of the membrane. The potentials were measured with an L & N K₂-type potentiometer in combination with a Hartmann and Braun galvanometer having a current sensitivity of 10^{-12} amp./mm/m.

If the correct value of B.I.P. is being measured, it should be almost independent of the concentration provided that both the ions have equal activities on the two sides of the membrane. Tables I and II record the data of measurements of B.I.P. over a fairly wide concentration range. The mobility ratios, calculated from the B.I.P. values, are also shown in the tables.

TABLE I

Bi-ionic potentials and calculated mobility ratio of Na⁺-K⁺ system.

Molality (K ⁺ /Na ⁺).	Activity (K ⁺ /Na ⁺).	E.M.F. (Ionac.C-200).	U_K/U_{Na} .	E.M.F. (IR-100).	U_K/U_{Na} .	E.M.F. (IR-130).	U_K/U_{Na} .
0.1/0.1	0.079/0.080	12.0 mv	1.61	16.0 mv	1.89	12.5 mv	1.63
0.05/0.05	0.042/0.042	12.1	1.61	16.2	1.88	12.3	1.62
0.02/0.02	0.0178/0.0178	12.0	1.61	16.3	1.87	12.3	1.62
0.01/0.01	0.0092/0.0092	12.1	1.61	16.2	1.88	12.2	1.61
0.005/0.005	0.00475/0.00475	12.2	1.61	16.2	1.88	12.1	1.60
0.002/0.002	0.00194/0.00194	12.1	1.61	16.0	1.88	12.3	1.62
0.001/0.001	0.00098/0.00098	12.0	1.61	16.0	1.88	12.0	1.61

TABLE II

Bi-ionic potential and calculated 'mobility ratio' of different union systems.

Molality. (A/B)	Activity. (A/B)	E.M.F. (Ionac-A-300)	U_A/U_B .	E.M.F. (IR-4B)	U_A/U_B .	E.M.F. IR-400	U_A/U_B
System : Iodide (A)/bromide(B).							
0.1/0.1	0.079/0.079	6.0 mv	1.26	6.9 mv	1.31		
0.05/0.05	0.042/0.042	6.2	1.27	7.0	1.31		
0.02/0.02	0.0178/0.0178	6.0	1.26	7.0	1.31		
0.01/0.01	0.0092/0.0092	6.1	1.27	6.9	1.31		
0.005/0.005	0.00475/0.00475	6.0	1.26	6.9	1.31		
0.002/0.002	0.00194/0.00194	6.0	1.26	6.5	1.29		
0.001/0.001	0.00098/0.00098	6.0	1.26	6.0	1.28		
System : Bromide (A)/chloride(B).							
0.1/0.1	0.079/0.079	7.0	1.31	6.5	1.29	7.0 mv	1.31
0.05/0.05	0.042/0.042	7.2	1.32	6.5	1.29	6.5	1.29
0.02/0.02	0.0178/0.0178	7.0	1.31	6.3	1.28	7.0	1.31
0.01/0.01	0.0092/0.0092	7.0	1.31	6.1	1.27	7.0	1.31
0.005/0.005	0.00475/0.00475	7.2	1.32	6.0	1.26	6.8	1.30
0.002/0.002	0.00194/0.00194	6.9	1.31	6.0	1.26	7.0	1.31
0.001/0.001	0.00098/0.00098	6.5	1.30	5.8	1.25	6.5	1.29

TABLE II (contd.)

Molality. (A/B)	Activity. (A/B)	E.M.F. (Ionac. A-300)	U_A/U_B .	E.M.F. (IR-4B)	U_A/U_B .	E.M.F. (IR-400)	U_A/U_B .
System: Nitrate (A)/chloride (B).							
0.1/0.1	0.088/0.079	3.1mv	1.31	1.7mv	1.24	6.8mv	1.52
0.05/0.05	0.0385/0.042	4.5	1.30	3.1	1.23	8.2	1.50
0.02/0.02	0.0174/0.0178	5.8	1.28	4.5	1.22	9.6	1.48
0.01/0.01	0.0081/0.0082	6.3	1.29	5.1	1.23	9.1	1.44
0.005/0.005	0.0047/0.00475	6.0	1.28	5.0	1.23	8.5	1.41
0.002/0.002	0.00192/0.00194	5.9	1.27	4.5	1.20	9.0	1.43
0.001/0.001	0.00097/0.00098	5.8	1.27	5.0	1.23	8.5	1.46
System: Bromide (A)/nitrate (B).							
0.1/0.1	0.079/0.088	2.5 (Br ⁻ +ve)	0.95	3.0 (Br ⁻ +ve)	0.97	2.5 (Br ⁻ +ve)	0.95
0.05/0.05	0.042/0.0385	0.4 (")	0.90	1.3 (")	0.97	1.0 (")	0.95
0.02/0.02	0.0178/0.0174	1.5 (NO ₃ ⁻ +ve)	0.92	1.5 (NO ₃ ⁻ +ve)	0.92	1.2 (NO ₃ ⁻ +ve)	0.93
0.01/0.01	0.0092/0.0091	1.1 (")	0.95	2.0 (")	0.92	1.3 (")	0.94
0.005/0.005	0.00475/0.0047	1.0 (")	0.95	2.1 (")	0.91	1.1 (")	0.95
0.002/0.002	0.00194/0.00192	0.9 (")	0.96	1.6 (")	0.93	1.2 (")	0.95
0.001/0.001	0.00098/0.00097	0.9 (")	0.96	1.5 (")	0.93	1.4 (")	0.94

* (Br⁻+ve) or (NO₃⁻+ve) means that the calomel electrode dipped in the bromide or nitrate ion solution responds as the positive terminal.

FIG. 1. System KCl—NaCl across cation-exchange resin membrane.

The effect of varying the activity ratios on the intramembrane mobility ratios was also studied by following the procedure of Wyllie and Kannan⁹ who maintained the concentration of one of the components fixed and varying the concentration of the other. The results can be best interpreted by graphical methods, whereas the equation,

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_M}{a_N} \cdot \frac{U_M}{U_N}$$

predicts, if U_M/U_N is independent of changes made in the activities, a_M and a_N , of the external solutions, the plot of E against $\log a_M$, for constant a_N should give a straight line. Similarly, a straight line should be obtained for the analogous case in which a_M is maintained constant and a_N is varied. The graphs are shown in Figs. 1-3.

FIG. 2. System KCl—NaCl across Amberlite IR-120 cation-exchange resin membrane.

DISCUSSION

In spite of the limitations of B.I.P. measurements, the results are in good agreement with the theoretical values. Thus Tables I and II show that B.I.P.s and hence the mobility ratios remain fairly constant as the theory predicts. In the case of Br⁻ and NO₃⁻ ion

system (Table II), the interesting point to be noted is that as the concentration is varied on both sides, the sign of the membrane charge alters, but the B.I.P. and the calculated mobility ratios remain fairly constant.

The straight line graphs represented in Figs. 1-3 indicate constancy of mobility ratio even if the concentration ratios of the ions concerned are varied within a certain range. Calculated mobility ratios, however, show that these tend to vary with the change in the activity ratio of the two ions concerned. This is because of the logarithmic relation between E.M.F. and activity and mobility ratios, so that the mobility ratio becomes a sensitive function of the E.M.F.

FIG. 3. System KBr—KNO₃ across anion-exchange resin membranes.

When the ionic strength on the two sides of the membrane becomes widely different, the difference in the activity of water⁹ will cause a difference of potential. The transport of water through resin membranes is now an established fact¹⁰.

Thus it becomes evident that two conditions are essential for determination of activity of each of two critical ions in a mixture, namely, at least two membranes having mobility ratios as different as possible for the particular pair of critical ions and their constancy over the concentration range to be studied.

10. Bergsma and Staverman, *Disc., Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 21, 61.

In the case of resin membranes studied by us, the first requirement is not guaranteed, since these do not show sufficiently wide 'mobility ratio'. Mobility ratios are, however, fairly constant over the activity range studied. The resin membranes could therefore be used to mixtures containing different proportions of critical ions. The results are recorded in Tables III and IV.

TABLE III

E.M.F. values in mixture of K⁺ and Na⁺ ions in different proportions with K⁺-form membrane.

No.	Inside soln.	Outside soln. (mixture).		Observed E.M.F. (m.v).			Theoretical E.M.F.
	K ⁺ ion,	K ⁺ ion,	Na ⁺ ion.	IR-100.	Ionac-C-200.	IR-120.	
(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)
1	0.1 m	0.05 m	0.00050 m	16.3	16.3	16.3	16.3 mv
2	0.1	0.05	0.0010	16.2	16.3	16.3	16.3
3	0.1	0.05	0.0025	15.5	15.7	15.9	16.3
4	0.1	0.05	0.0050	15.2	15.2	15.2	16.4
5	0.1	0.05	0.0100	13.5	13.5	13.5	16.6
6	0.1	0.05	0.0250	10.3	10.3	10.2	17.1
7	0.1	0.05	0.0500	6.0	5.3	5.3	17.8

Column 'b' of each table records the molality of the particular ion which is maintained constant. The resin was also of the same form as this ion. In columns 'c' and 'd' are shown respectively the molalities of this particular ion and that of the other (called the second ion) in mixture with it. The observed E.M.F.'s. recorded with three different membrane electrodes are shown in columns 'e', 'f', and 'g'. All the membranes give nearly the same E.M.F. values, showing that a fairly steady state has been attained. The comparison with the theoretical E.M.F.s. is made in the last column 'h'. The theoretical values have been calculated on the basis of the assumption that the second ion affects the activity of the first in so far as the ionic strength is changed, but does not register its activity on the membrane itself which has been initially saturated with the first ion on both sides.

As will be noticed from the data, this assumption is hardly valid as the concentration of the second ion increases. Activities of the two ions in the mixture have been varied between 1:100 and 1:1 approximately. The second ion begins to affect the E.M.F. as soon as its activity is above a certain value. This seems to depend, according to the results obtained by us, on the nature of the two ions concerned. This for Na⁺-K⁺ mixture, discrepancies occur as the a_{Na^+}/a_{K^+} ratio exceeds 1:10. For the anion pair studied, these particular limiting ratios are: $a_{Cl^-}/a_{Br^-} = 1:10$; $a_{NO_3^-}/a_{Br^-} = 1:10$; $a_{Cl^-}/a_{NO_3^-} = 1:25$; $a_{Br^-}/a_{NO_3^-} = 1:25$. As already pointed out, these inferences appear to be independent of the nature of resin membranes.

The obvious reason for the observed discrepancy is that the resin membrane on the side of the mixture is not only registering the activity of the principal ion with which the membrane is saturated but also that of the other ion. Consequently, the value of the 'mobility ratio' of the ion pair concerned becomes significant. The values of the mobility

TABLE IV
E.M.F. values of different anion systems in mixtures in different proportions.

Systems A and B mixture with A form membrane.	Serial No. (a)	Inside solution (b) Molality (A), (b) Molality (B)	Outside solution (mixture) (d) Molality (A), (d) Molality (B)	Observed E. M. F. (mv)		Theoretical E.M.F. (mv) (h)		
				IR-4B.	IR-400			
Nitrate (A) and bromide (B) ion mixture with nitrate form membrane	1	0.1	0.025	0.0005	29.0	28.5	20.5	29.9
	2	0.1	0.025	0.0010	28.9	29.8	29.6	29.9
	3	0.1	0.025	0.0025	28.0	26.5	26.5	30.3
	4	0.1	0.025	0.0100	21.7	21.0	21.5	30.9
	5	0.1	0.025	0.0250	13.5	14.0	14.0	32.5
Nitrate (A) and chloride (B) ion mixture with nitrate form membrane	1	0.1	0.025	0.0005	29.0	29.6	29.0	29.9
	2	0.1	0.025	0.0010	29.5	29.5	29.8	29.9
	3	0.1	0.025	0.0050	26.0	27.0	27.5	30.3
	4	0.1	0.025	0.0100	22.0	21.0	22.5	30.9
	5	0.1	0.025	0.0250	15.0	15.0	15.2	32.5
Bromide (A) and nitrate (B) ion mixture with bromide form membrane	1	0.1	0.025	0.0005	32.8	32.7	32.9	32.9
	2	0.1	0.025	0.0010	32.7	32.5	32.8	32.9
	3	0.1	0.025	0.0025	30.0	30.5	30.0	33.0
	4	0.1	0.025	0.0050	25.0	25.5	25.5	33.1
	5	0.1	0.025	0.0250	16.0	14.5	16.0	34.1
Bromide (A) and chloride (B) ion mixture with bromide form membrane	1	0.1	0.025	0.0005	32.8	32.9	32.6	32.9
	2	0.1	0.025	0.0010	32.9	32.8	32.7	32.9
	3	0.1	0.025	0.0025	30.5	31.5	32.0	33.0
	4	0.1	0.025	0.0050	25.8	25.5	26.1	33.1
	5	0.1	0.025	0.0250	16.2	14.0	16.8	34.1

ratio have therefore been calculated for those cases where the discrepancies have been observed. The 'mobility ratio' values have been calculated, using Marshall's equation for the mixture of a pair of critical ions. The results are recorded in Tables V and VI.

TABLE V

Calculated 'mobility ratios' (U_{K^+}/U_{Na^+}) from the mixture of K^+ and Na^+ ions.

Serial No of Table VI.	IR-100.	Ionno-C-200.	IR-120.
3	1.52	2.03	2.95
4	2.10	2.10	2.10
5	1.57	1.57	1.57
6	1.67	1.67	1.64
7	1.74	1.61	1.61

The 'mobility ratio' values are not constant, but vary rather irregularly within not too wide values. Comparing these values with those calculated from B.I.P. (Tables I and II), where the mobility ratios are more or less constant, a possible cause of these variations may be suggested. According to the conditions set forth for B.I.P. measurements, the state of affairs is as follows:

Here the two faces of the membranes are saturated with two different ions, M^+ and N^+ , contacting respectively M^+ and N^+ ions in solution. But in the experiments described above with mixture of ions, the situation is somewhat different and may be visualised as follows:

According to kinetic considerations, so long as the concentration of N^+ is very small, the concentration potential is established very rapidly between M^+ ions of different concentrations on both sides. The presence of N^+ ions changes only the ionic strength of the medium and hence the activity of M^+ ion in the mixture. As the number of N^+ ions increases with its concentration, the influence exerted by them cannot, however, be ignored, compared to M^+ ion. But under the conditions of the experiments, an equilibrium on the side of the mixture is hardly attained. Consequently a constant ratio is not likely to be expected.

The work of Spiegler and Coryell¹¹ shows the ionic mobilities of two ions within a cation-exchange resin to be dependent on the concentration of each. This, in turn, as Wyllie and Kannan⁹ suggested, means that they will be dependent on the activities of the cations on the exchange sites of the membrane faces and, in consequence, on the relative activities of the cations and the ionic strengths of the ionic solutions in contact with the faces.

TABLE VI

Mobility ratio values (U_A/U_B) calculated from the $E.M.F.$ values studied in mixture of anions.

Serial No. referred to in Table IV.	Ionac-A-300.	IR-4B.	IR-400.	Ionac-A-300.	IR-4B.	IR-400.	Ionac-A-300.	IR-4B.	IR-400.	Ionac-A-300.
3	0.90	0.69	0.89	1.13	1.60	1.70	0.78	0.94	0.78	0.98
4	0.99	0.90	0.96	1.02	0.90	1.10	0.52	0.85	0.55	0.61
5	1.00	1.04	1.04	1.12	1.12	1.14	0.90	0.80	0.90	0.92

Nitrate (A) and bromide (B) ions. Nitrate (A) and chloride (B) ions. Bromide (A) and nitrate (B) ions. Bromide (A) and chloride (B) ions.

McLean *et al.*² also have noted that equations derived on the basis of the simple Henderson equation give rise, in the case of mixed monovalent and bivalent ion solutions, to mobility ratio values which are markedly dependent on concentration.

In comparison to the resin membranes, those prepared from clays show a much wider variation of mobility ratios. This is perhaps due to the fact that the "steric factor", partly responsible for transport of ions within the membrane, will be much more pronounced in the crystalline clays than in the non-crystalline resins.

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